

**INTERNATIONAL LINGUISTIC TERMS IN NATIVE LANGUAGE (UZBEK)
ENCYCLOPEDIAS: BALANCING SCIENTIFIC ACCURACY AND NATIONAL
IDENTITY**

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Abstract. This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of presenting international linguistic terms in encyclopedic dictionaries of the native language (uzbek). It examines the role of international terms in scholarly communication, their relationship with national equivalents, and the principles that should be followed in compiling encyclopedic works. Using a number of examples from linguistic terminology, the study considers the issue of balancing scientific accuracy and accessibility for a wider audience.

Keywords: linguistics, terminology, encyclopedia, native language, national identity.

INTRODUCTION

“The successful resolution of all issues related to terminology largely depends on the compilation and publication of terminological dictionaries that comprehensively cover the terms of each field, especially explanatory terminological dictionaries. In such dictionaries, it is important to determine how accurately, completely, and clearly each term conveys the essence of the concept, object, or phenomenon it denotes. This makes it possible to assess the extent to which a term meets the required standards and fulfills its intended function. Until such dictionaries are created, various negative phenomena within the terminological system will continue to persist. These include, for example, the use of more than one term to express the same concept and, conversely, the use of a single term to denote several different concepts or phenomena. Other problems include the existence of terms that fail to express the essence of a phenomenon correctly, fully, and precisely, as well as similar shortcomings in terminology” [1:3].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Therefore, one of the foremost tasks of specialists in every field is to compile explanatory terminological dictionaries, as well as encyclopedic dictionaries, that cover the terminology of their respective disciplines as comprehensively as possible and identify the terms that accurately, fully, and clearly reflect the essence of the phenomena they denote.

As a result of globalization processes, the status and importance of international terminology in the fields of science and technology have been steadily increasing. In the field of linguistics as well, many concepts are expressed through international terms. Such terms facilitate scientific communication among scholars from different countries and contribute to the establishment of terminological uniformity. At the same time, the question of how international terms should be presented in scientific literature and encyclopedias written in national languages remains one of the important theoretical and practical issues.

An encyclopedia in the native language serves not only as a reference source but also as a reflection of a nation's scientific thinking and terminological culture. Therefore, when presenting international terms in an encyclopedia, it is necessary to maintain a balance between scientific accuracy, national identity, and comprehensibility. Furthermore, as a scientific and educational resource, an encyclopedia should convey the meaning of a particular concept clearly, precisely, and concisely.

Even today, the issue of nationalizing international terms and using them in scientific discourse remains one of the pressing concerns in Uzbek linguistics. This process began after the Uzbek language was granted the status of the state language. Linguist and academician Abduqodir Hojiyev explained his preparation of a revised edition of the *Explanatory Dictionary of Linguistic Terms* with nationalized terminology as follows:

“The author revised and expanded the above-mentioned explanatory dictionary of linguistic terms by removing unsuitable terms and replacing Russian and Russian-international terms, wherever possible, with Uzbek terms that were already in use or had been newly created. The resulting dictionary is the one presented to you today. We would especially like to note that nearly one-third of the Russian and Russian-international linguistic terms currently in use, as well as compound terms containing such words, have been completely Uzbekized.” [1:4.]

This statement demonstrates the efforts undertaken in Uzbek linguistics to adapt international terminology to the national language while preserving scientific precision and ensuring broader accessibility for Uzbek-speaking users.

The scholar also includes international terms in the dictionary. However, whenever an Uzbek equivalent exists, he presents the Uzbek variant as the main entry. For example, **LINGVISTIKA** (fran. Linguistique > lot. Lingua – til) ayn. **Tilshunoslik**; **SEMEMA** – ayn. **Leksik ma’no**.

Alongside specialized dictionaries, establishing principles for the presentation of terms in encyclopedic dictionaries is also one of the important directions of terminological policy.

RESULTS

The question of whether international terms should be fully nationalized or retained in their original form remains a matter of debate in many languages. In linguistic terminology, however, international terms constitute an integral part of scientific communication. For example, the term *homonym* is widely used in world linguistics. In Uzbek linguistics, it has a national equivalent, *shakldosh so‘zlar* (“words of identical form”). Presenting only the term *shakldosh so‘zlar* in explanatory dictionaries of linguistic terms may weaken the connection with international scholarly literature. Conversely, providing only the term *homonym* may make comprehension difficult for some readers.

Therefore, when compiling such dictionaries, it is advisable to present both the international term and its national equivalent together. For example: *omonimlar* (*shakldosh so‘zlar*), *sinonimlar* (*ma‘nodosh so‘zlar*), *antonimlar* (*zid ma‘noli so‘zlar*), and *lingvistika* (*tilshunoslik*). Likewise, other terms may be presented in the same manner.

This approach not only preserves the integrity of the scientific terminological system but also facilitates users' understanding and helps prevent confusion arising from terminological variation among learners and readers.

For individuals with an academic background, understanding international terms generally does not present any difficulty. Therefore, the use of national equivalents of international terms is not widespread in scientific publications intended for specialists beyond the school level. However, when introducing terminology to school-age students and helping them develop an initial understanding of linguistic concepts, the use of national equivalents is considered appropriate.

Taking this into account, school textbooks and popular educational literature more frequently employ terms such as *shakldosh so‘zlar* (*omonimlar*), *ma‘nodosh so‘zlar* (*sinonimlar*), *shakldoshlik* (*omonimiya*), and *ma‘nodoshlik* (*sinonimiya*). These terms are valuable because they express the essence of the concepts in a simple and transparent manner.

Creating a national equivalent for every international term does not always produce effective results. A substitute term must satisfy several requirements: it should accurately convey the meaning of the concept, conform to the internal principles of the language, gain acceptance among specialists, and remain understandable to the wider public. If a national equivalent fully reflects the meaning of an international term, it may be presented as the main entry in an encyclopedia. However, it would not be advisable to exclude from an encyclopedia those international terms that are actively used in international scientific communication and do not have well-established Uzbek equivalents.

Let us now examine how international linguistic terms and their national equivalents are explained in some dictionaries of linguistic terminology.

In “*Tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug‘ati*” [1:8] **xatboshi** – this linguistic term is explained as follows: “**ХАТ БОШИ**. Матн (текст) нинг дастлабки қаторини бироз ўрин (уч харф ўрни) қолдириб бошлаш” va “**АБЗАЦ** (нем. Absatz > absetzen – сурмоқ, нари сурмоқ). 1. айн. Хат боши.” In “*O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati*” [3:40/26] explained as follows: “**ХАТБОШИ** Bosma yoki yozma matnda xatning dastlabki qatoridan bi roz joy tashlab boshlash, абзас. Xatboshidan yozmoq. — 1) 5-modda: ikkinchi qismining uchinchi xatboshisi “korxonalarining obligatsiyalari” degan so‘zlar bilan almashtirilsin. Gazetadan.” va “**АБЗАЦ** [nem. Absatz < absetzen – yangi satrdan boshlash] Matn (tekst) ning dastlabki qatorini biroz o‘rin (uch harf o‘rni) qoldirib boshlash; xatboshi, satrboshi. Yangi abzasdan yozmoq.”

“АБЗАЦ англ. paragraph, фр. alinéa, нем. Absatz. Отрезок письменной речи от одной красной строки до другой, функционирующий как сверх фразовое единство или сложное синтаксическое целое.” In “Словарь лингвистических терминов” [2:24.] was been given the above definition of a *abzas*, but does not define it as a *xatboshi*.

DISCUSSION

In the *Native Language (uzbek) Encyclopedia*, there is no need to provide the form **abzas** for the term **xatboshi**, as is done in the dictionaries mentioned above. It is important for readers to know the purely Uzbek name of this concept. Naturally, in this encyclopedia the term should not merely be explained; rather, in keeping with the nature and purpose of the work, it should be given a broad, consistent, precise, and easily understandable definition that is accessible to the general public.

There is also variation in the naming of the term **shakldoshlik**, with two different variants being used.

ОМОНИМИЯ. Бирдан ортиқ тил бирлигининг талаффуз ва тузилиши жиҳатдан бир хил бўлиши ҳодисаси. Омонимиянинг лексик омонимия (к.); фразеологик омонимия (к.); грамматик омонимия (к.) ва б. турлари бор [1:75]. **ОМОНИМІЯ** исп. homonimia. Звуковое совпадение двух или более разных языковых единиц. Омонимия звуковая. Омонимия лексическая. Омонимия окончаний. Омонимия падежных форм. Омонимия фразеологизмов. Омонимия частичная. Омонимия флексий ложная англ. sham inflexional homonymy. Омонимия конечных слогов у ряда слов, незави сима от их фонеморфологической определенности [2:276]. **SHAKLDOSHLIK.** Shakldoshlik – til birliklarida tovush va yozuv tomoni bir xil, ammo bir-biriga bog‘liq bo‘lmaydigan ma’no ifodalash hodisasi [4:249].

In the *Native Language (uzbek) Encyclopedia*, however, by including the Uzbek equivalent term **shakldoshlik**, the following definition would create a clear, simple, and scientific understanding of the term: “**Shakldoshlik** Yozilishi va aytilishi bir xil, lug‘aviy ma’nolari har xil bo‘lgan birdan ortiq til birliklari o‘rtasida yuzaga chiqadigan leksik hodisa, shunday birliklar o‘rtasidagi munosabat. Shakldoshlik qo‘shimcha, so‘z, ibora doirasida kuzatiladi. Bu birliklarning tushunilishi esa tinglovchidan bilim, mahorat, tafakkur hamda fahmni talab qiladi”. (**Shakldoshlik** is a lexical phenomenon that occurs between two or more language units that are identical in spelling and pronunciation but different in lexical meaning; it refers to the relationship between such units. Shakldoshlik can be observed at the level of affixes, words, and phrases. Understanding these units requires knowledge, skill, thinking ability, and comprehension from the listener.)

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, providing national equivalents of international linguistic terms in the *Native Language Encyclopedia* primarily helps prevent the formation of a perception among school-age children that such terms and the concepts they represent are complex or difficult.

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